

ՀԱՅԱՍՏԱՆԻ ՀԱՆՐԱՊԵՏՈՒԹՅՈՒՆ

ՄԵՐՐԱԲՅԱՆԻ ԱՆՎԱՆ
ԲԺՇԿԱԿԱՆ ԻՆՍՏԻՏՈՒՏԻ
ՏԵՂԵԿԱԳԻՐ

ВЕСТНИК
МЕДИЦИНСКОГО ИНСТИТУТА
ИМ. МЕГРАБЯНА

BULLETIN
OF THE MEDICAL INSTITUTE
AFTER MEHRABYAN

ԳԻՏԱԿԱՆ ՏԵՂԵԿԱԳԻՐ
НАУЧНЫЙ БЮЛЛЕТЕНЬ

ՀԱՏՈՐ 1 ԾՈՄ

ՄԵՐՐԱԲՅԱՆԻ ԱՆՎԱՆ ԲԺՇԿԱԿԱՆ ԻՆՍՏԻՏՈՒՏ

Выходит два раза в год на русском, армянском и английском языках

Բ.Տ. ՂԱՐԻԲՋԱՆՅԱՆ գլխավոր խմբագիր, Հայաստան, Երևան
 Լ.Գ. ՄԵՂՐԱԲՅԱՆ գլխավոր խմբագրի տեղակալ, Հայաստան, Երևան
 Ա. ԿԼԻՍՍԱՐՈՎԱ գլխավոր խմբագրի տեղակալ, Բուլղարիա, Վառնա

ԽՄԲԱԳՐԱԿԱՆ ԽՈՐՀՈՒՐԴ

ՂԱՐԻԲՋԱՆՅԱՆ Բ.Տ. (ԲԳԴ, պրոֆեսոր, Երևան), ՇՈՒՔՈՒՐՅԱՆ Ա. Կ. (ԲԳԴ, պրոֆեսոր, Երևան), ԱՊՐԻԿՅԱՆ Ս. Վ. (ԿԳԴ, պրոֆեսոր, Երևան), ՄԱՐԳԱՐՅԱՆ Է. Ա. (ՔԳԴ, պրոֆեսոր, Երևան), ՄՆԱՑԱԿԱՆՅԱՆ Վ. Հ. (ՔԳԴ, պրոֆեսոր, Երևան), ՂԱԶԱՐՅԱՆ Ս. Հ. (ՔԳԹ, դոցենտ, պատասխանատու խմբագիր, Երևան),

ГАРИБДЖАНЫН Б. Т. – главный редактор, Армения, Ереван
 МЕГРАБЯН Л. Г. – заместитель главного редактора, Армения, Ереван
 КЛИССАРОВА А. – заместитель главного редактора, Болгария, Варна

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ

ГАРИБДЖАНЫН Б. Т.(ДМН, профессор, Ереван), ШУКУРЯН А. К. (ДМН, профессор, Ереван), АПРИКЯН С.В. (ДБН, профессор, Ереван), МАРКАРЯН Э. А.(ДХН, профессор, Ереван), МНАЦАКАНЯН В. А. (ДХН,профессор,Ереван), КАЗАРЯН С. А. (КХН,доцент,ответственный редактор,Ереван).

GHARIBJANYAN B.T. – Editor – in – chief, Armenia , Yerevan
 MEHRABYAN L. G. – Deputy Editor, Armenia, Yerevan
 KLISSAROVA A. – Deputy Editor, Bulgaria, Varna

EDITORIAL COUNCIL

GHARBJANYAN B.T. (DMS, Professor, Yerevan), SHUKURYAN A. K. (DMS, Professor, Yerevan), APRIKYAN S. V. (DBS, Professor, Yerevan), MARGARYAN E. A. (DChS, Professor, Yerevan), MNATSAKANYAN V. H. (DChS, Professor, Yerevan), GHAZARYAN S. H. (Phd, Docent, Executive Editor, Yerevan).

M. Georgieva¹,
Em. Mutafova², A. Dokova²

¹ University Hospital
"St. Marina" – Varna

² Medical University – Varna

MANAGING THE CHANGE IN BULGARIAN HEALTHCARE SECTOR THROUGH PROJECT MANAGEMENT

Key words: *project management, hospital, hospital management.*

The analysis of the modern health care management and the health care systems in the different countries reveals that there is running continuing change because of the factors of the environment. This change is the result from the dynamic social, economic, political, organizational and structural changes which set new and higher requirements for the management of health care sector.

Since 1998 the Bulgarian healthcare system is being reformed and new theories for healthcare management were adopted and implemented. The development of the doctrines and the concept of health provoked permanent change. They included change in the structure, management, role and financing of the health organizations, which became market players and had confronted new legislation, more informed and powerful consumers, higher community expectations and pressure for transparency. In the same time they became responsible for offering high quality medical services, respecting patient's rights, observing personnel and partner's satisfaction and achieving medical and financial effectiveness in short and long term.

During the reform new problems had aroused. The main one was the inadequate and insufficient financing of the health organizations. The shortage of money for health together with the permanent change flow in Bulgarian healthcare sector urged health organizations to search and use new managerial instruments.

In the past years particularly important became one of them – the projecting or the project management – a tool for understanding and managing the change and preventing chaos in the organization and the system as a whole. Even though it is an important lever for raising additional financing for the health organizations, it is still underestimated and poorly used in the health sector.

In the health care system the vision of lots of people is needed because the change is critical and it refers the social interrelations relevant to the functioning of the particular system. That is why project management invaded the daily practice of managers in health care. The project management is the carrier rocket of the change and gives the stimuli for long-lasting processes, going beyond the purpose and the deadline of the project.

Method: individual questionnaire, mailed directly to health care managers

Object of investigation: health care institutions and organizations in Bulgaria

Period of observation: 1995 – 2004 ?.

Scope of the research: 25 projects, accomplished in 22 institutions, as it follows: university structures – 9, university hospitals – 8, hospitals for acute treatment – 4, governmental and non-governmental national institutions – 4.

RESULTS FROM THE RESEARCH AND DISSCUSSION

Most of the projects were developed on institutional level (48 %) and this reflects the new role of the health organizations on market and the responsibilities for doing "healthcare business". At local level there are least projects (8 %). The reason for this is the lack of structures, which can consult and support this activity. Only 16 % projects are on national level while 28 %—on international. The last number shows the positive influence of foreign partner in the projecting as well the lack of experience amongst Bulgarian organizations in this activity.

The total value of a project differs from 250 € to 440 000 € and it shows that in health care even little improvements are important and useful.

The main indicators for success of the projects according to the health care managers in Bulgaria are:

- Achieving the objects of the project
- Satisfaction of patients and/ or the personnel
- Interest and value for the public
- Improving the activities in the organization
- Scientific value – dissertations, publications, scientific researches

Mostly the projecting is implemented in several main areas like:

- Medicine – **including biology, endocrinology, cardiology, neurology, orthopedics, toxicology, pharmacy, physiology, and surgery.**
- New medical specialties **with an accent to the general medicine.**
- Healthcare management – **predominantly in healthcare insurance, professional organizations, and private medical practice.**
- Hospital management – **projects concern hospital stay, quality of healthcare services, nurse administration, and hospital hygiene.**

Detailed picture of the different kinds of projects is presented on figure 1:

fig.1: KINDS OF PROJECTS

Most often the project team is local (in 80 % of cases) and only in 20 % is international. The participants are mostly up to 10 (60 %), while up to 50 and up to 500 are respectively 16 %. Only 8 % included up to 1500. This is prompted by the reason that a small group (up to 10 people or organizations) is the easiest for coordination, allows fast communication between the participants, has good performance and achieve best results in short and middle term projects.

Average duration of the projects is 2 years, with prevalence the short-term projects until 1 year. The longest project observed is 7 years (still running), and the shortest one – shorter than 1 year. The possible reason for the absence of long-term projects could be: lack of sufficient know-how in the field of project management; lack of sufficient funding and ability to support the project unassisted; personnel rejection or lack of interest. Clarifying the real reason could be done in a future investigation.

The methods of funding the projects were predominantly internal funding (72 %) vs. external funding was used in 28 % of the cases. This is still insufficient indicator and shows lack of knowledge of health care managers in Bulgaria how to apply and perform projects with financing from European and international programs and grants.

The main difficulties in projecting were defined. The main one were pointed as finding of funding for the project (6,75 points). Designing the project, accomplishing it, accounting, control and finding partners are also difficult to some extent. (see figure 2). Other difficulties are out of date national legislation; lack of good coordination of supply of resources for the project; way of thinking of the participants in the project. Most of the difficulties indicated were objective and only two of them were subjective but with poor influence – interpersonal conflicts in project government and intercultural differences between partners.

fig.2: MAIN DIFFICULTIES IN PROJECT MANAGEMENT

CONCLUSIONS

1. Most of projects are on institutional level. There is a lack of projects on local level.
2. The total value of a project differs from 250 € to 440 000 €.
3. The main indicators for success are:
 - Achieving the objects of the project
 - Satisfaction of patients and/ or the personnel
 - Interest and value for the public
 - Improving the activities in the organization
 - Scientific value
4. The projects are directed to:
 - **Medicine**
 - **New medical specialties**
 - **Healthcare management**
 - **Hospital management**
5. The project teams are mostly local (80 %) and include up to 10 participants.
6. Average duration of the projects is 2 years, with prevalence the short-term projects until 1 year.
7. The methods of funding the projects are predominantly internal (72 %).
8. The main difficulties in projecting are
 - finding of funding for the project
 - designing the project
 - accomplishing the project
 - accounting
 - control
 - finding partners

The project management in Bulgarian health care sector is still insufficient. There is a lack of knowledge and experience in this field amongst the health care managers. There is a lack of structures that can support this activity at institutional, local and national level. A possible solution in this direction can be in medical universities and university hospitals convert to project management coordination centers that provide methodical guidance (including theoretical and practical help) to the small and medium health care organizations in Bulgaria.

REFERENCES

1. Heerkens, Gary R. Project management. New York: McGraw-Hill, 2002.
2. Planning and management for health, Report on a European conference Euroreport and studies, N102, WHO, Regional office for Europe, Copenhagen, 1986.
3. Frame, J. Davidson. The new project management: tools for an age of rapid change, complexity, and other business realities. San Francisco: John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2002.

4. Lewis, James P. Fundamentals of project management. New York: AMACOM Books, 1995.
5. Georgieva, M. Strategic management of hospital and its tools – methods for economical analysis of performance, international conference “Is planning in crisis”, 26–28 of may 2005, Svishtov, Bulgaria.
6. McKee, M. Hospitals in a changing Europe, WHO, Open University Press, Philadelphia, 2002.

Summary: The shortage of money for health together with the permanent change flow in Bulgarian healthcare sector urged health organizations to search and use new managerial instruments. The present work analyses the implementation of project management in hospital government in Bulgaria. There had been defined different aspects of this activity which includes level of the projects, number of participants, amount of funding, duration, field of application, and main difficulties in the process of project management. As an obstacle has been pointed lack of knowledge and experience among hospital managers as well as absence of structures that can support the development and putting into practice of new projects. A possible solution in this direction has been pointed out which include converting medical universities and university hospitals to project management coordination centers that can provide methodical guidance (including theoretical and practical help) to the small and medium health care organizations in Bulgaria.

D. Stavrev, M. Ianeva, H. Bozov EXPERIMENTAL MODEL FOR GRADUAL INTOXICATION WITH CO OF RATS FOR OPTIMIZING TREATMENT REGIMES OF HYPERBARIC OXYGENATION	60
Antoniya Dimova, Maria Rohova IMPACT OF THE FINANCING METHODS ON HOSPITAL PRODUCT QUALITY	68
M. Georgieva, Em. Mutafova, A. Dokova MANAGING THE CHANGE IN BULGARIAN HEALTHCARE SECTOR THROUGH PROJECT MANAGEMENT	73
Yoana Kiselova, Diana Ivanova, Bistra Galunska, Trifon Chervenkov, Daniela Gerova, Tatyana Yankova POLYPHENOL CONTENT AND IN VITRO ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY OF AQUEOUS-ALCOHOLIC EXTRACTS FROM BULGARIAN HERBS	78
Zh. Rangelova, E. Moutafova, T. Kostadinova, D. Tomov SOCIAL STRATIFICATION AND HEALTH	84
Antoniya Dimova, Maria Rohova, Miroslav Popov HOSPITAL ORGANISATIONAL AND MANAGERIAL CULTURE	89
Г.А. Еганян, Э.К. Диланян ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ СБК «НАРИНЭ» (В КАПСУЛАХ) ДЛЯ ПРОФИЛАКТИКИ И ЛЕЧЕНИЯ РЯДА ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ	94
S.H.Minasyan, E.V.Kobalyan, A.I. Gevondyan, S.H. Ghazaryan, F.T. Greenaway, J.R.J. Sorenson ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY OF Mn(II) CHELATES OF ETHYL ESTERS OF SALICYLIDEN-SCHIFF BASES OF AMINO ACIDS	102
Софья Абазян ФАКТОР УСПЕХА В ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ АПТЕЧНОГО БИЗНЕСА	104
Ш.Г. Африкян ПРОКАЛЬЦИТОНИН УНИВЕРСАЛЬНЫЙ МАРКЕР ИНФЕКЦИОННОГО ВОСПАЛЕНИЯ	110
Л.Г. Меграбян, Н. А. Гаспарян ПРОЕКТ ДИСТИАНЦИОННОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ ПО ОКАЗАНИЮ ПЕРВОЙ МЕДИЦИНСКОЙ ПОМОЩИ	114

ՄԵՋՐԱԲՅԱՆԻ ԱՆՎԱՆ
ԲԺՇԿԱԿԱՆ ԻՆՍՏԻՏՈՒՏԻ ՏԵՂԵԿԱԳԻՐ

•
ВЕСТИК
МЕДИЦИНСКОГО ИНСТИТУТА ИМ. МЕГРАБЯНА

•
BULLETIN
OF THE MEDICAL INSTITUTE AFTER MEHRABYAN

Տպագրությունը՝ օֆսեթ: Չափսը՝ 70x100 1/16: Թուղթը՝ օֆսեթ:
Ծավալը՝ 7.5 տպ. մամուլ:

«ԶԱՆԳԱԿ-97» ՀՐԱՏԱՐԱԿԶՈՒԹՅՈՒՆ
375051, Երևան, Կոմիտասի պող. 49/2, հեռ.՝ (+37410) 23-25-28,
ֆաքս՝ (+37410) 23-25-95, էլ. փոստ՝ info@zangak.am, էլ. կայք՝ www.zangak.am
Գրախանութ՝ Երևան, Խանջյան փող. 29, հեռ.՝ 54-06-07, էլ. կայք՝ www.book.am